

Analysis of Low Voltage Ride Through Capability in Multiport Converters for Soft Open Point Applications

K. A. A. Mohammed · P. Mattavelli · T. Caldognetto · D. Biadene · P. Magnone

Abstract The growing power demand, combined with intermittent renewables, presents significant challenges for distribution networks. This paper focuses on multiport converters as key devices for enhancing flexibility and optimizing existing infrastructure. Multiport converters are designed to facilitate enhanced power flow control on meshed networks and extended operation in case of faults. As an example of multiport converters, traditional soft open points (SOPs) are explored in this study, configured in a back-to-back (B2B) circuit. SOPs are investigated for their vulnerabilities, particularly in fault scenarios disrupting the converter responsible for regulating the dc link voltage, so fault ride through (FRT) approach is required to handle this situation. Furthermore, low voltage ride through (LVRT) requirements mandate the converter to remain connected during voltage sags, to prevent undesired tripping and provide reactive power support to the grid. To address these challenges, a unified control logic is proposed, devised to handle both LVRT requirements and FRT conditions. This approach ensures system connection during voltage sags and provides reactive power support to the grid. Simulation results presented in this paper validate the effectiveness of the proposed unified control logic, discussing its significance in enhancing the reliability of distribution networks and meeting the LVRT requirements.

1 Introduction

The rise of renewable energy is reshaping electrical grids, particularly due to increased distributed energy resources (DERs) in low and medium-voltage grids. DERs integration poses technical challenges. Current efforts in the energy sector, led by researchers and policymakers, focus on creating effective solutions to transition from traditional fossil-fuel based power systems to green energy systems [1], [2].

While traditional network reinforcement is a viable option for increasing capacity, its drawbacks, including high costs and time-consuming implementation, make it less favorable. This situation emphasizes the need for innovative approaches to dynamically improve the utilization of existing assets and redirect power flows through less burdened circuits. To bridge the gap between radial and mesh operations, we propose adopting a flexible mesh configuration facilitated by multiport converters to enable enhanced power flow control and reliability in case of faults. As an illustrative example of multiport converters, this paper explores SOPs in-depth, which replaces normally open points (NOPs). Unlike the simple open/close functionality of NOPs, SOPs present advanced features, including flexible control of active power exchange between connected feeders, reactive power provision at the interfaced ports, and immediate post-fault supply restoration to support isolated loads on a feeder by transferring power from an adjacent feeder. Consequently, SOPs introduce greater flexibility to current distribution networks, to release capacity on existing feeders and enhance customer efficiency and service quality [3].

SOPs typically involve the connection of two ac terminals through a back-to-back (B2B) circuit configuration, illustrated in Fig. 1. However, this setup is susceptible to vulnerabilities, especially when a fault occurs, potentially leading to SOP failure. This problem is particularly severe when it disrupts the converter responsible for regulating the dc

K. A. A. Mohammed
University of Salerno
e-mail: kmohammed@unisa.it

K. A. A. Mohammed · P. Mattavelli · T. Caldognetto · D. Biadene · P. Magnone
DTG – University of Padova
Stradella S. Nicola 3, 36100 Vicenza, Italy
e-mail: khaledawadallahahmed.mohammed@studenti.unipd.it

Fig. 1: Comprehensive control architecture for a two-port soft open point (SOP).

link voltage. Moreover, low voltage ride through (LVRT) requirements necessitate the converter to remain connected during voltage sags, preventing undesired disconnections that may jeopardize the overall system stability. Additionally, the converter is expected to offer reactive power support to the grid during such instances.

LVRT control strategies for grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) systems under abnormal conditions should encompass rapid voltage fault detection, determination of active and reactive current setpoints, and mitigation of overcurrent failures through current limitation [4]. The IEEE Std. 1547-2018 specifies LVRT requirements applicable to this scenario, outlining voltage ride-through criteria that mandate grid-tied inverters to remain operational for a specified duration during a grid fault. The voltage duration profile varies among countries, taking into account factors such as voltage drop depth, fault time, voltage recovery time, and final voltage magnitude [5].

Besides staying connected during grid faults, DERs can contribute by injecting or absorbing reactive power with the aim of aiding grid voltage recovery. This contribution is measured by the ratio of reactive current to rated current. The underlying principle is similar to voltage regulation through reactive power control, where DER inverters absorb reactive power during voltage swells and inject reactive power during voltage sags. However, specific requirements for reactive power support, such as the ratio of reactive current to voltage sag/swell and the maximum required reactive power, vary among countries [6].

To comply with LVRT requirements, accurate detection of voltage sags, characterized by temporary decreases in grid

voltage, is crucial. Various techniques are available in scientific literature of variable complexity and response time. These methods address challenges such as unbalanced voltage sags, phase-angle shifts, and the presence of harmonics. Careful selection of a voltage sag detection approach is essential for ensuring correct and reliable LVRT compliance and timely identification of voltage sags [7]. A summary of various methods, each with distinct features and suitability, is provided in Tab. 1 based on their detection times.

Effectively regulating the dc link voltage relies significantly on the grid synchronization of the dc/ac slave converter. In the event of an islanding or short-circuit fault at the ac terminal of the dc-voltage-regulation master converter, the ability to sustain the dc link voltage diminishes, leading to the eventual collapse of the entire SOP system [8]. In this case, no active power can be supplied to the dc link capacitor by the master converter, so there is no regulation for the dc link voltage. The responsibility for controlling the dc link voltage should be transferred to the other converter to achieve the regulation and enable the converter to support reactive power to the grid at fault for better stability [5] and to reduce the possibility of voltage collapse [9], [10]. In a similar case, in multi-terminal SOP, the dc link connects several converters, and the loss of the master station, which is responsible for regulating the dc link voltage, causes the power flow between the healthy feeders to stop. Again, the responsibility for controlling the dc link voltage should be transferred to one of the slave converters. To tackle this challenge, a unified control logic is implemented herein, ensuring both LVRT requirements and FRT conditions. While both LVRT and FRT deal with the system's response to abnormal condi-

Table 1: Voltage Sag Detection Techniques [11], [12].

Detection Technique	Detection Time
RMS-Based Approach	Up to 40 ms
Variants of rms (s-rms, m-rms, r-rms)	Half of One Cycle
Fast Fourier transform (FFT)	One Full Cycle
Reduced fast Fourier transform (RFFT)	Approximately 3 ms
Hybrid Structure Combining Instantaneous Sag Detector and rms Variation Detector	Within 2.0 ms
Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference Frame Phase-Locked Loop (DDSRF-PLL)	12 ms
Enhanced Phase-Locked Loop (EPLL)	80 ms
Moving Average Filter with Phase-Locked Loop (MAF-PLL)	20 ms
Harmonic Footprint Detection	Less than 1 ms

tions, LVRT is specifically about voltage sags, whereas FRT encompasses a broader range of fault conditions. The proposed work ensures sustained connectivity during voltage sags and enhanced reactive power support, aiming to improve reliability and reduce the risk of voltage collapse by upholding dc voltage control in the case of a master station failure (Fig. 2).

2 SOP's Structure and Control

The bidirectional power flow capability of the converter facilitates its utilization in distribution networks, regardless of whether renewable and energy storage systems are integrated. This feature enhances the operational efficiency and dynamic response of distribution systems, thereby addressing the evolving needs of modern power grids [3]. In scenarios involving the interconnection of two or more distribution feeders, a typical approach employs a two-stage, back-to-back voltage source converter (VSC) as shown in Fig. 1 [14] or the multi-terminal configurations in [15]. This configuration yields numerous advantages, notably the establishment of a robust meshed distribution network that augments control capabilities and resilience to overcome dynamic operational challenges. The converters also facilitate islanded operation, black start capabilities, and efficient battery integration, reducing overall battery capacity requirements and optimizing resource utilization across interconnected feeders.

In the scope of our current study, both the voltage source converters utilized are three-phase three-wire converters. The control is implemented in the $\alpha\text{-}\beta$ frame. As in [16], the controller consists of two parts: a hybrid controller for power and dc voltage control and an ac-side current controller. The hybrid controller can switch between active power control mode and dc voltage control mode according to the state of the VSC. The current controller can regulate the ac-side

Fig. 2: Simplified flowchart of the logic to handle LVRT and FRT conditions.

current of the VSC using proportional-resonance (PR) controllers. The controller operates in the $\alpha\text{-}\beta$ frame. Fig. 1 shows the overall control architecture.

The controller parameters are designed using a simplified model of the VSC. The main objective is to achieve reliable dc voltage control and to implement precise power regulation within the SOP. Furthermore, to improve the system's response during power disturbances, a power feedforward loop is implemented at the voltage control loop's output. This feedforward loop integrates the power reference signal into the control scheme. The inner current loops are implemented using a proportional resonant (PR) compensator within the $\alpha\text{-}\beta$ frame [13].

3 Simulation Results

This section presents the simulation results of the SOP under various operational scenarios. The SOP under investigation shares the construction and the control structure illustrated in Fig. 1, with the corresponding parameters detailed in Tab. 2. The investigated scenarios include voltage sag at the master's grid, voltage sag at the slave's grid, and zero voltage at the master's grid with voltage sag at slave's grid.

Fig. 3 illustrates the outcomes of the simulation under a voltage sag scenario at the rectifier side, where the master converter is positioned. At instant 0.4 s, a voltage sag is applied at the master's side, causing the port voltages to equal 0.4 p.u. and 1 p.u. at the master and slave sides, respectively.

Table 2: Simulation Parameters

Grid's Voltage, $V_{LL,rms}$	400 V
Line frequency, f_L	50 Hz
Rated power, S_{rated}	300 kVA
PWM Frequency, f_{PWM}	10 kHz
Converter's inductor, L	0.004 H
DC link capacitor, C_{dc}	30 mF

Given that the master's grid voltage exceeds the minimum threshold, the master converter seamlessly continues its role in regulating the dc link voltage. However, the reduction in the master's voltage prompts an increase in master current to uphold a consistent power transfer between the two ports of the SOP. To prevent an uncontrolled increase in output current, the control loop employs a saturation block, enforcing boundaries for both upper and lower current limits. Consequently, the power transferred to the feeder at the slave side surpasses that transferred from the master side, leading to a discharge of the dc link capacitor. To avoid this issue, the power transfer reference between the ports is adjusted to zero during the voltage sag, as depicted in Fig. 3(e). Consequently, the slave converter's current diminishes to zero, as depicted in Fig. 3(c).

A current reference is derived from the power reference signal exchanged between the two ports. This current reference is integrated into the output of the dc link voltage controller, enhancing the system's ability to swiftly reach a steady state following power disturbances and update events, as demonstrated in Fig. 3(b).

In alignment with the IEEE Std. 1547-2018 [5], providing reactive power support to the grid during a sag is desirable for stability maintenance. In Fig. 3(e), it is evident that reactive power is supplied to the grid at the master side, with the maximum value of the delivered reactive power defined by the converter's rated current, illustrated in Fig. 3(d). The imposed maximum current limit is steadfastly maintained at 612 A.

Similar to Fig. 3, Fig. 4 shows the simulation results under a voltage sag scenario, this time occurring at the inverter side, designated as the slave converter. At 0.4 s, a voltage sag transpired at the slave's side, adjusting the port voltages to 1 p.u. and 0.4 p.u. at the master and slave sides, respectively. As the voltage sag is at the slave's side, the master converter persists in its role of regulating the dc link voltage.

Under normal conditions, the slave converter governs the regulation of power transfer between the two ports. However, the decrease in the slave's voltage prompts a surge in the slave's current to uphold consistent power transfer. This surge, in case of need, is curtailed by limiting the current signals in the control loop using a saturation block in the simulation, enforcing boundaries for both upper and lower current limits. Consequently, at 0.4 s, the power transferred to the feeder at the slave side diminishes, falling below the power transferred to the dc link from the master side. The dc voltage controller requires time to rebalance the power, resulting in an overshoot in the dc link capacitor voltage, as depicted in Fig. 4(b).

To support reactive power on the grid at the slave side, the active power reference between the two ports is adjusted to zero during voltage sag. Reactive power is then supported

Fig. 3: Voltage sag at the master's grid (rectifier side). (a) Slave's/master's rms voltage. (b) dc link voltage. (c) Slave's grid current. (d) Master's grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

Fig. 4: Voltage sag at the slave's grid (Inverter side). (a) Slave's/master's rms voltage. (b) DC link voltage. (c) Slave's grid current. (d) Master's grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

Fig. 5: Zero voltage at the master's grid and voltage sag at the slave's grid. (a) Slave's/master's rms voltage. (b) DC link voltage. (c) Slave's grid current. (d) Master's grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

instead, as shown in Fig. 4(e). Consequently, the master converter's current reduces to nearly zero, as indicated in Fig. 4(d).

Fig. 4(e) and Fig. 4(c) highlight that, the maximum value of the supplied reactive power is constrained by the converter's rated current, with the maximum current limit steadfastly maintained at 612 A.

In Fig. 5, the master's voltage declines to zero at 0.4 s, while the slave voltage decreases to 0.2 p.u. In this scenario, if the master's voltage falls below the minimum threshold, regulating the dc link voltage with the master converter becomes infeasible. Hence, the slave converter assumes responsibility for managing the task during the voltage sag. Consequently, the master's priority signal (S) for dc link control is set to zero.

The active power reference between the two ports is set to zero. With the master's voltage at zero, the reactive power transfer to the master's grid becomes zero, while a constrained value remains for the slave's reactive power. This transfer of control from master to slave, combined with the active power adjustment, ensures stable dc link voltage regulation.

4 Conclusions

This paper has systematically investigated the operational capabilities of the soft open point system within distribution networks, specifically addressing challenges posed by voltage sags and faults. Through comprehensive simulations, the study shows the system's adeptness in dynamically adjusting power transfer references between converters, ensuring stability and compliance with low voltage ride through standards. The unified control strategy is effective in maintaining precise regulation of dc link voltage during voltage sag events at both master and slave converters. The simulation outcomes confirm the effectiveness of the proposed SOP system in achieving the reliability of distribution networks.

Acknowledgements This work acknowledges the support of the Ph.D. program in Photovoltaics at the University of Salerno, where I am currently enrolled. Additionally, the research is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the project 'iPLUG' with grant agreement number 101069770.

References

1. D. Debnath, K. Chatterjee, "Two-stage solar photovoltaic-based stand-alone scheme having battery as energy storage element for rural deployment", *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, pp. 4148–4157, 2014.
2. J.M. Carrasco, L. Garcia Franquelo, J.T. Bialasiewicz, E. Galván, R.C. Portillo Guisado, M.A. Martín Prats, J.I. León, N. Moreno-Alfonso, "Power-electronic systems for the grid integration of renewable energy sources: A survey", *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, Vol. 53, No. 4, pp. 1002–1016, 2006.
3. W. Cao, "Soft open points for the operation of medium voltage distribution networks", *PhD Thesis*, Cardiff University, 2015.
4. E. Afshari, G.R. Moradi, R. Rahimi, B. Farhangi, Y. Yang, F. Blaabjerg, S. Farhangi, "Control Strategy for Three-Phase Grid-Connected PV Inverters Enabling Current Limitation Under Unbalanced Faults", *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 8908–8918, Nov 2017.
5. Photovoltaics, Distributed Generation and Storage, Energy, "IEEE standard for interconnection and interoperability of distributed energy resources with associated electric power systems interfaces," *IEEE Std*, vol. 1547, pp. 1547–2018, 2018.
6. J.A. Fuentes, M. Cañas, A. Molina, E. Gómez, F. Jiménez, "International Review of Grid Connection Requirements Related to Voltage Dips for Wind Farms", *Proceedings of the International Conference on Renewable Energies and Power Quality*, 2007.
7. C. Ma, F. Gao, G. He, G. Li, "Fast voltage detection method for the voltage ride through operation of grid-tied renewable energy generation systems", *2014 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition-APEC 2014*, pp. 386–391, 2014.
8. Y. Qi, Y. Li, W. Li, H. Deng, Y. Tang, "Autonomous Control of Soft Open Point for Distribution Network Reliability Enhancement", *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 3127–3137, Jun 2023.
9. D.I. Brandao, F.E.G. Mendes, R.V. Ferreira, S.M. Silva, I.A. Pires, "Active and reactive power injection strategies for three-phase four-wire inverters during symmetrical/asymmetrical voltage sags", *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 2347–2355, 2019.
10. R. Rai, B. Singh, "Converter Control During Low Voltage Ride Through Operation for Grid-Interfaced Solar PV Battery Assisted System", *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 9181–9191, 2022.
11. S. Xu, Y. Xue, L. Chang, "Review of power system support functions for inverter-based distributed energy resources—standards, control algorithms, and trends", *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 2, pp. 88–105, 2021.
12. V.A. Katić, A.M. Stanisavljević, "Smart detection of voltage dips using voltage harmonics footprint", *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 5331–5342, 2018.
13. A. Timbus, M. Liserre, R. Teodorescu, P. Rodriguez, F. Blaabjerg, "Evaluation of Current Controllers for Distributed Power Generation Systems", *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 654–664, 2009.
14. Y. Li, X. Pei, Z. Chen, M. Yang, Z. Lyu, C. Wang, "The Steady-State and Fault Ride-Through Control Strategies of Soft Normally Open Point in Distribution Network", *2018 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, pp. 1146–1150, 2018.
15. M. Yang, X. Pei, Y. Li, "Multi-port Coordinated Control Strategy of SOP in Distribution Network", *2020 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)*, pp. 2333–2337, 2020.
16. M. Yang, X. Pei, M. Zhang, Y. Zhang, H. Wang, "An Improved Master-Slave Control Strategy for Automatic DC Voltage Control Under the Master Station Failure in MTDC System", *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1530–1541, 2022.